

APPENDIX I

Study	Main research questions	Sample	Methodological needs	Visual participatory approach	Miro board
<p>Study I: Health information behavior and digital well-being of individuals with social anxiety disorder.</p>	<p>RQ1: What behaviors do people affected by social anxiety disorders exhibit in terms of seeking, finding, experiencing, evaluating, and avoiding (mental) health information?</p> <p>RQ2: Are health information interactions influenced by the subjective digital well-being of people affected by social anxiety disorder?</p>	<p>N=22</p>	<p>An approach in the interview is needed that leads to people feeling encouraged to share / open up about their everyday life interaction and practices with technology. As everyday use of technology is mainly performed through smartphones or tablets and app use, an approach is needed to map specific apps to associated interactions and make it visually accessible throughout the interview.</p>	<p>Gathering the apps used through visually depicting them serves as a basis for a deeper examination about participants' actual technology interaction and subjective assessment of their digital well-being during the interview.</p>	<p>Miro board 1 (figure 1)</p>
			<p>An approach is needed that helps participants speak about feelings and emotions associated with specific technology interactions, such as app use or lack thereof, as well as associated health information behaviors.</p>	<p>Encouraged participants to specify feelings associated with app use by allocating the apps into categories: (1) "makes me feel good", (2) "makes me feel partly good/not good", and (3) "makes me feel bad."</p>	<p>Miro board 2 (figure 2)</p>
			<p>An approach is needed that engages participants to think about information sources they currently use or have used in the past and about information needs they had or currently have.</p>	<p>Implement an approach which leads participants to collect used health information sources. This serves as a basis to stimulate hidden knowledge about sources used and also associated information needs.</p>	<p>Miro board 3 (figure 3)</p>

<p>Study II: Health information behavior towards false information and perception of scientificity</p>	<p>RQ1: What critical incidents trigger the dissemination of (false) health information? RQ2: What factors lead to information on health topics being perceived as scientific?</p>	<p>N=21</p>	<p>An approach is needed to encourage participants to share sensitive information about how they interact with (false) health information, and stimulate participants' explicit and tacit knowledge that is sometimes challenging to recall.</p>	<p>Engage participants to share situations and experiences of health information interactions by developing a personal health information infrastructure together. Through the visualized actors and sources used, past and present health information interactions can stimulate the recall of past situations. Furthermore, reflections on information interactions and behavior can be stimulated.</p>	<p>Miro board 4 (figure 4)</p>
			<p>It needs an approach to stimulate discussion about perceived scientificity of specific health resources to better understand which indicators lead people to the assumption of which health sources identified as scientific or trustworthy and which not.</p>	<p>Encourage participants to share their opinion on science and scientificity. By visualizing specific resources and letting participants rate them as “scientific,” “partly scientific,” and “not scientific,” participants can engage in participatory discourse through valuing their opinions and assessments.</p>	<p>Miro board 5 (figure 5)</p>

Table 1. Study design, methodological needs, and implementation of visual participatory elements within the presented studies.

APPENDIX II

Figure 1. Miro board 1 with (from left to right) blank post-its, app collection, smartphone/tablet for gathering the apps used, trash can for the apps implemented but not used.

Figure 2. In Miro board 2 participants were encouraged to specify or classify feelings associated with the specific apps used by having them allocate those apps into categories (from left to right: "makes me feel good", "makes me feel partly good/not good", "makes me feel bad").

Figure 3. In Miro board 3 participants were encouraged to share information needs (questions) and information sources / channels that they have used in the past or use in present.

Figure 4. Miro board 4 aimed to map participants' personal health information infrastructures with potential sources to choose from (in gray) and blank cards (post-its) to add sources used (left). The red rings (left) helped to mark the main sources and arrows (not shown here) to visualize relationships between sources/actors.

Figure 5. Miro board 5 was used for assessing the scientificity of different health information sources by assigning colored buttons (“scientific”, “not scientific,” or “partly scientific”) to stimulate discussion about scientificity of health information resources and criteria for the subjective assessment of scientificity.

APPENDIX III

3 My personal mental health information infrastructure

A What sources or channels do I use when I have questions about my (mental) health?

B What questions do I have or have had about my mental health?

Figure 6. Example of the personal health information infrastructure of participant P05 (study I).

1 From whom or where do you get health information?

Trust in information source (+ reasons)
(categories were created by P17)

Reception and exchange of health information
(size = frequency)

Figure 7. Example of the personal health information infrastructure of participant P17 (study II).